

A General Approach to Authenticated Key Establishment Based on Homomorphic Secret Sharing

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This paper addresses the problem of establishing a secure communication channels between parties in a multiparty environment. Most of well-known key establishment protocols used in practice are based on Diffie–Hellman problems and require significant computational costs. Therefore, key pre-distribution protocols are preferred for resource-constrained devices. In this paper, we consider protocols of this type based on secret sharing and propose a general approach using the homomorphic property of secret sharing schemes. Examples of such protocols are given and their security properties are analyzed. We also prove some interesting side results — there are no perfectly secure two party key agreement and joint multiparty threshold decreasing protocols in a public channels setting. Finally, we rise a problem whose solution will allow for lightweight and secure connections between any devices.

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1. Introduction

This paper addresses the problem of establishing a secure communication channels between parties in a multiparty environment. Recently, ad-hoc networks, such as Internet of Things (IoT), Internet of Drones (IoD) or Flying Ad-Hoc Networks (FANET), Vehicular Ad-Hoc Networks (VANET), Mobile Ad-Hoc Networks (MANET), Wireless Sensor Networks (WSN), Smart Home and so on, have been actively developed and used in everyday life. Features of such networks are high mobility and limited resources of nodes. Therefore, classical cryptographic protocols for establishing secure communication channels are not always applicable.

Most of well-known authenticated key establishment (AKE) protocols used in practice are based on Diffie-Hellman problems and require significant computational costs. Therefore, key pre-distribution protocols are preferred for resource-constrained devices. The first protocols

of such type were developed more than forty years ago. Let there be n fixed parties in the network. In the simplest case, any party holds all $n - 1$ pre-distributed keys to establish secure channels with others. But this is very inconvenient and not applicable for dynamic systems, especially when the number of parties is huge.

In modern key pre-distribution protocols [1], each party i gets a fixed length secret value (*secret key*) s^i and, usually, associated *public key* pk^i , which allow to authenticate this party and establish a secure keys with others. So, such protocols always consist of two stages: a registration stage and a key establishment stage. At the registration stage, the Key Distribution Center (KDC) registers the party, binds it with some unique public identifier and/or public key pk^i , and gives it a fixed length secret value s^i . All pairs (pk^i, s^i) are generated according to some cryptographic scheme which allows to establish a secret key between two or more parties at the second stage. At the key establishment stage, two or more parties together generate secure key without assistance of KDC or another trusted third party. If three or more parties obtain

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common secret key after this stage, such a key pre-distribution protocol is usually called *Group Authenticated Key Exchange* (GAKE), otherwise it is called Multi-Party Pairwise Authenticated Key Establishment (MPAKE). Obviously, in GAKE we assume, that all group members are trusted or corrupted parties can be identified and excluded from protocol execution. On the other hand, in MPAKE we assume, that any adversary cannot find the secret key established between any two uncorrupted parties. So, MPAKE is more powerful in this security sense, and further we concentrate on it.

In this paper, we consider MPAKE based on secret sharing and propose a generalized approach using the homomorphic property of secret sharing schemes. Examples of such protocols are given and their security properties are analyzed. We show, that any party AKE can be expressed in terms of secret sharing. Finally, we rise a general problem whose solution will allow for lightweight and secure connections between any devices.

The paper is organized as follows. In Section 2 we provide related work, Section 3 contains basic definitions and notation, and the main results are presented in Section 4. Finally, we discuss them in conclusions.

2. Related work

Multi-party pairwise key establishment (a part of key management) plays a central role in securing distributed systems. When dealing with resource constrained devices, the key pre-distribution protocols is the best choice for this purpose. Blom seminal key pre-distribution scheme [2] and Blundo [3] scheme, which are based on symmetric polynomial, are widely used. In Blom scheme, the KDC chooses a symmetric polynomial $f(x, y)$ over a finite field \mathbb{F}_q . At the registration stage, it gives the i -th party a “share” $s^i(y) = f(ID_i, y)$, where ID_i is an identifier of the party i . To establish a common key with the party j , the party i simply calculates the value $K_{ij} = s^i(j)$. The key establishment stage in this

protocol is even non-interactive.

Another type of key pre-distribution protocols uses the technique called *probabilistic key sharing*, introduced by Mitchell and Piper [4]. The main idea is to divide the key space into several key pools U_i , $i = \overline{1, n}$, of small size and distribute these pools among all parties. After that, if the party i wants to establish a key with the party j , these parties communicate to find the intersection of their pools $U_{ij} = U_i \cap U_j$. If $U_{ij} = \emptyset$, then the party i finds disjoint secure paths $Path_1, \dots, Path_l$ to the party j , generates key K_{ij} by herself, shares it as $K_{ij} = k_1 \oplus k_2 \oplus \dots \oplus k_l$, and transmit each share k_u to the party j via the path $Path_u$, accordingly. In this case, all intermediate parties play a role of distributed key transportation centers. There are several such protocols in the literature [5–8].

The common disadvantage of all key pre-distribution protocols is the necessity of Trusted Setup procedure. Moreover, the protocols based on symmetric bivariate polynomials can be used only until the number of corrupted parties do not exceed predefined threshold value. In probabilistic key sharing, each party needs to have enough memory for storing their key pools.

In [9] we proposed a modification of Blom key pre-distribution protocol to achieve *freshness*. In short, we replaced the symmetric polynomial $f(x, y) \in \mathbb{F}_q[x, y]$ by the polynomial $g(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{F}_q[x, y, z]$ that is symmetric only on the first two variables, i.e. $g(x, y, z) = g(y, x, z)$ for any arguments $(x, y, z) \in \mathbb{F}_q^3$. The parties secret values are $h^i(y, z) = g(ID_i, y, z)$, $i = \overline{1, n}$. If the party A wants to agree on common secret key with the party B , she executes the one round protocol, presented in Table 1.

Note, that the protocol (see Table 1) achieves not only freshness of the common secret key and has the same threshold perfect secrecy as original Blom protocol, but also implicit one-side authentication (i.e. the party B is sure that the message M^A and, accordingly, the key K_{AB} was formed by the party A). But an adversary Eve can still perform the reply attack by forwarding old messages M^A to the party B . So, to overcome

this threat, one can propose to add explicit key confirmation round or use timestamp/counter instead of nonce at the first step of the protocol. Another disadvantage of this protocol is the relatively large amount of memory required by each party to store her secret.

In search of a solution in which each party requires a fixed small amount of memory to store the secret, the MPAKE protocol [10, 11] was developed. It utilizes the additive homomorphic property of linear secret sharing schemes and is based on an general idea that we explain later in Section 4. The price for the small memory size for storing secrets in this protocol is large communication overhead.

3. Preliminaries

3.1. Secret Sharing Schemes

Secret sharing scheme (SSS) allows to share a secret s among n parties in such a way that only a specified coalitions of them can together recover the secret. The “part of the secret” received by the party is called a *share*. In the majority of secret sharing schemes each party is given not only a share, but also public data strictly related to the share. We call this data the *public key* of the party.

All specified coalitions of the parties together form an *access structure*. They are called authorized. The remaining coalitions form a *denial structure*. They are called *forbidden*. If all forbidden coalitions obtain nothing about the secret (in the strong theoretical sense), the secret sharing scheme is called *perfect*. Perfect scheme is *ideal*, if the size of each share and the size of the secret are the same. SSS is called t -out-of- n threshold ((t, n) -threshold), if any coalition of t or more parties can recover the secret.

Formally, let $I = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ be the set of all parties and $\Gamma \subseteq 2^I$ be the access structure. Secret sharing scheme for the access structure Γ and the secret $s \in \mathcal{S}$ is defined by the triple of algorithms: $SSS = (Gen, Share, Recover)$. The probabilistic algorithm *Gen* generates all public

parameters of SSS including the public keys of the parties. The probabilistic algorithm *Share* maps the secret $s \in \mathcal{S}$ to the vector of shares (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n) , $s_i \in \mathcal{S}_i, \forall i \in I$. The deterministic algorithm *Recover* reconstructs the secret s from given vector of shares using corresponding public keys of the parties.

The first secret sharing schemes were proposed independently in 1979 by Shamir [12] and Blakely [13]. Shamir used the Lagrange polynomial interpolation while Blakely used projective vector spaces to construct a scheme. Both schemes are proved to be ideal. In the Shamir scheme, a trusted party called *dealer* performs the *Share* algorithm. The dealer randomly choose secret polynomial $f(x) = \sum_{i=0}^{t-1} a_i x^i$ of degree $t - 1$ over the finite field \mathbb{F}_q , where the secret $s = f(0)$. Then he sends the party i a share $s_i = f(i)$, $i = \overline{1, n}$. To recover the secret, t or more parties together solve corresponding linear equation system or use a Lagrange’s interpolation formula.

Nowadays there are several general approaches for constructing secret sharing schemes. The most popular and well-studied are linear approach [14–16] and modular approach [17, 18]. In the linear SSS the secret S can be found by solving the linear equation system. Both Shamir and Blakely schemes are linear. Modular SSS was firstly proposed by Mignotte [17] and Asmuth and Bloom [18] in 1983. It is based on Chinese remainder theorem.

Secret sharing scheme is called *additively homomorphic* if it satisfies the following condition:

$$s + c = Recover(s_1 + c_1, s_2 + c_2, \dots, s_n + c_n),$$

$$\text{where } (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n) = Share(s, \Gamma), \\ (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) = Share(c, \Gamma).$$

3.2. Adversary model

A coalition of dishonest parties that collude and exchange data, is considered as a single adversary. We consider a threshold adversary that

Table 1: Interactive modified Blom AKE protocol.

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1. The party A selects randomly the nonce $N \in \mathbf{F}_q$ and calculates the key $K_{AB} = h^A(ID_B, N)$;
 2. If two separate keys K_{Enc} and K_{MAC} are needed for encryption and message authentication, correspondingly, the party A derives them from the key K_{AB} ;
 3. The party A sends the message $M^A = ID_A || N || MAC_{K_{MAC}}(ID_A || N)$ to the party B ;
 4. The party B calculates the key $K_{AB} = h^B(ID_A, N)$ and verifies MAC on M^A .
-

can corrupt no more than t parties. Commonly, the model of corruption is *static* meaning that corrupted parties are fixed ahead of the protocol, but it is also possible to consider *adaptive* adversaries that decide during the protocol execution which parties to corrupt.

In this paper we use well-known definition of security for multiparty computation protocol from the book of Cramer *et al.* (see [16]). Namely, we require two conditions:

Perfect correctness With probability 1, all parties receive outputs that are correct based on the inputs supplied.

Perfect privacy Any adversary learns no information about secret values of uncorrupted parties from executing of the protocol, regardless of their computing power.

We also consider two types of adversary — outside and inside. The first one can only see all protocol messages, the second is able to compromise some parties, knows their secrets and, if it is malicious, does not follow the protocol during execution. In addition, we are interested in two basic attacks on key establishment protocols: a *Man-in-the-Middle* (MITM) attack and a *Known Key Attack* (KKA). MITM allows an adversary to insert herself between participants during the protocol execution in such a way that at the end of the protocol, the parties think that they are communicating with each other, but in fact, all communication goes through the adversary. The beneficial Diffie-Hellman (DH) protocol [19] suffers from this attack. But almost all key pre-distribution protocols, including mentioned in this paper, are protected

against MITM as the adversary needs to know the secrets of the parties to successfully carry out this attack. A known key attack involves the adversary somehow learning the final shared key and, based on it and the protocol messages, trying to extract information about the long-term secrets (keys) of the parties. KKA is successful, if it leaks some information about the secrets. In Diffie-Hellman protocol, the knowledge of the common key still leads to computationally hard problem. In the Blom-like protocol, if the adversary collects t or more different keys assigned to the fixed party i , she can find the secret of this party. Thus, KKA attack is successful. We see that none of these known protocols protect against both attacks.

Lastly, in modern AKE protocols the *freshness* property of the key is most important. This ensures that all sessions with the same long-term secrets return different shared keys. The Diffie-Hellman protocol does not provide freshness, so many different modifications of this protocol exist. The Blom protocol also defines persistent shared keys between any pair of parties, and our modification [9] fixes this.

4. Main results

First, we consider a classical two-party key agreement protocol executed in d communication rounds. Most known protocols run with $d = 1$ or $d = 2$. Let Alice (the party A) and Bob (the party B) want to establish a common secret key through insecure channel, and the adversary Eve (the party E) can do anything except forming messages of A and B . In any 2-party AKE both parties generate some secret random values or uses their static keys. In the latter case, if

the parties do not use any randomness, such a protocol may even be non-interactive ($d = 0$), but does not have freshness property. Blom key pre-distribution protocol is just of this type.

Let Alice sends to Bob the message M_i^A at round i , and Bob answers with the message M_i^B , $i = \overline{1, d}$. In the case $d = 1$ and $M_1^B = \emptyset$, i.e. Bob does not answer to Alice, this kind of key agreement is, in fact, a key transport protocol. Let also ID_A , s^A and ID_B , s^B be the identifiers and the secret values (keys) kept by Alice and Bob, correspondingly. Denote by $G^A = (g_1^A, g_2^A, \dots, g_d^A)$ the vector of transformations that Alice performs during the protocol execution to produce her messages, i.e. $M_i^A = g_i^A(s^A, ID_A, ID_B, M_{i-1}^B, \dots, M_1^B)$, $i = \overline{1, d}$. The similar notation G^B we use for Bob. Further, Alice computes a common key K_{AB} using some known deterministic function F^A , her secret s^A and messages received from Bob, i.e. $K_{AB} = F^A(s^A, M_1^B, \dots, M_d^B)$. Bob does the same, but uses his function F^B , his secret s^B and Alice's messages. First, we show, that if both parties generates their secrets independently and by themselves, then the key agreement protocol can only be computationally secure.

Theorem 1 *Let the parties generate their secrets independently and by themselves. Then any d -round key agreement protocol executed between them can only be computationally secure.*

PROOF

First, let us assume that to compromise a common key, an adversary needs to find the secret of one of the parties. Otherwise, such a protocol is a priori insecure. If in order to find a secret an adversary needs to inverse one of the functions g_i^A , then we get a classic computationally secure protocol based on the strength of a one-way function.

We consider the case, when an adversary can polynomially find some value \hat{s} that corresponds to all messages M_i^A , i.e. $M_i^A = g_i^A(\hat{s}, ID_A, ID_B, M_{i-1}^B, \dots, M_1^B)$, $i = \overline{1, d}$. Then she finds the key K_{AB} . Indeed,

let $\hat{K}_{AB} = F^A(\hat{s}, M_1^B, \dots, M_d^B)$. We show that $\hat{K}_{AB} = K_{AB}$. Consider the conditional entropy $\mathbf{H}(K_{AB}|s^A, M_1^B, \dots, M_d^B) = 0$. Note, that $\mathbf{H}(K_{AB}|s^B, M_1^A, \dots, M_d^A)$ is also zero, and Bob calculates the same common key K_{AB} . It immediately follows, that $K_{AB} = F^A(\hat{s}, M_1^B, \dots, M_d^B)$ for any value \hat{s} that corresponds to all Alice's messages. ■

Remark 1. It is easy to see, that the Theorem 1 is true also in multiparty settings.

Further, let us look at the key agreement protocol from the secret sharing perspective. For simplicity, we consider the most popular case $d = 1$ and omit the subscripts in the notations of the parties messages, i.e. we will write M^A instead of M_1^A . Let the parties A and B generate by themselves or received from KDC their secret values s^A and s^B that correspond to some secret sharing scheme $\Sigma = (Gen, Share, Recover)$.

In the case of key transport, the secret sharing scheme Σ must allow the party A to form a common secret key using some function F^A which depends only on the secret value s^A , identifiers of A and B , and random values generated by the party A . There must exist the another function F^B for party B , that allows the party B to calculate the common secret key K_{AB} using only her secret value s^B , identifiers of A and B , and the message M^A received from the party A . Note, that the message M^A must hide both the secret value s^A and the key K_{AB} . In general, the functions F^A and F^B are not necessary private.

In the classical key transport protocol based on asymmetric encryption Alice uses an encryption function $F^A = Enc$ and Bob's public key pk^B as her "secret" value s^A , while Bob decrypts the message M^A using decryption function $F^B = Dec$ and his private key pr^B . In this scenario, both functions F^A and F^B are public, but only the Bob's secret value $s^B = pr^B$ is private, while Alice's value s^A is cryptographically bound with s^B and public.

The example of key transport protocol based on secret sharing is presented in [9] (see Table 1). In fact, it uses functional secret sharing scheme, where $s^A = F^A$, $s^B = F^B$, and the message M^A

contains identifier of A , random values of A and authenticates the message M^A to the party B .

In the case of key exchange, both parties form their messages M^A and M^B . The secret sharing scheme Σ must allow both parties to calculate their common secret key K_{AB} using, in general, different functions F^A and F^B , that depend only on the identifiers of A and B and the pairs (s^A, M^A) and (s^B, M^B) , correspondingly.

The key concept to perform two- or multi-party key agreement based on secret sharing is using an additive secret sharing homomorphism. Let the additively homomorphic secret sharing scheme Σ realizes a $(3, 4)$ -threshold access structure, and the parties A and B receive at the registration stage the pairs of shares (s_1^A, s_2^A) and (s_1^B, s_2^B) of some secret $s \in S$, respectively. At the same time, both parties register their identifiers ID_A and ID_B and associate with them the pairs of public keys (pk_1^A, pk_2^A) , (pk_1^B, pk_2^B) , correspondingly. To agree on common secret key at the key establishment stage they perform the protocol, presented in Table 2. Based on

the previous discussion, we conclude that the functions F^A and F^B correspond to the *Recover*, while the messages M^A and M^B are constructed using a *Share* function of the scheme Σ .

Theorem 2 *In the outside adversary setting, the protocol (Table 2) is perfectly secure authenticated key agreement.*

PROOF

First, we prove the correctness of the protocol (see Table 2). Let's look at the common key K_{AB} obtained by the parties. The party A calculates the key K_{AB} as the sum

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha + \text{Recover}(s_1^A + \beta_1, s_2^A + \beta_2, s_2^B + \beta_4, pk_1^A, pk_2^A, pk_2^B) \\ = \alpha + s + \beta. \end{aligned}$$

Indeed, as the threshold $t = 3$ and the scheme Σ is additively homomorphic, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Recover}(s_1^A + \beta_1, s_2^A + \beta_2, s_2^B + \beta_4, pk_1^A, pk_2^A, pk_2^B) &= \text{Recover}(s_1^A, s_2^A, s_2^B, pk_1^A, pk_2^A, pk_2^B) \\ &+ \text{Recover}(\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_4, pk_1^A, pk_2^A, pk_2^B) = s + \beta. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the party B calculates $K_{BA} = \beta + s + \alpha = K_{AB}$. That proves the correctness.

Further, consider an outside unbounded adversary E that tries to find the key K_{AB} , compromise the shares of the parties or perform *man-in-the-middle* (MITM) attack. First, the messages M^A and M^B perfectly hide the values of two shares s_1^A and s_2^B , as the sum of two independent uniformly distributed values is also uniformly distributed. For the same reason, these messages perfectly hide the values of α and β .

Next, we show that all values of the key K_{AB} are possible and uniformly distributed for

E . Note, that E knows two shares $(s_1^A + \alpha_1 + \beta_1)$ and $(s_2^B + \beta_4 + \alpha_4)$ of true key K_{AB} . But she has no information about the values of s_2^A , α_2 or their sum. The adversary E can choose any $\hat{\alpha}_1$ and determine corresponding $\hat{\alpha}_2$ using a triple of shares $(\hat{\alpha}_1, \alpha_3, \alpha_4)$ and $\hat{s}_1^A = s_1^A + \alpha_1 - \hat{\alpha}_1$. But any value of s_2^A is still possible. Thus, for any fixed pair $(\hat{\alpha}_2, \hat{s}_1^A)$ and fixed \hat{K}_{AB} the adversary E can find one corresponding share \hat{s}_2^A . This proves that the value of the key K_{AB} is uniformly distributed for E .

Finally, we show that the man-in-the-middle attack is impossible. It is true due the fact, that

Table 2: Two-party AKE based on homomorphic secret sharing.

1. The party A selects randomly some secret value $\alpha \in S$ and shares it with threshold $t = 3$ $Share(\alpha, t, pk_1^A, pk_2^A, pk_1^B, pk_2^B) = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \alpha_4)$. Then it sends the message $M^A = ID_A ID_B (s_1^A + \alpha_1) \alpha_3 \alpha_4$ to the party B ;
2. The party B selects randomly some secret value $\beta \in S$ and shares it with threshold $t = 3$ $Share(\beta, t, pk_1^A, pk_2^A, pk_1^B, pk_2^B) = (\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4)$. Then it sends the message $M^B = ID_B ID_A \beta_1 \beta_2 (s_2^B + \beta_4)$ to the party A ;
3. The party A calculates the key $K_{AB} = \alpha + Recover(s_1^A + \beta_1, s_2^A + \beta_2, s_2^B + \beta_4, pk_1^A, pk_2^A, pk_2^B)$;
4. The party B calculates the key $K_{BA} = \beta + Recover(s_1^A + \alpha_1, s_1^B + \alpha_3, s_2^B + \alpha_4, pk_1^A, pk_1^B, pk_2^B)$.

to correctly recover the key at steps 3 and 4 of the protocol (Table 2) from the vector of shares, the adversary E must use corresponding public keys and shares of the parties. Even if she is an insider, she can not substitute her own public keys and shares — this will give the incorrect result. For the same reason, successful completion of the protocol authenticates the parties to each other.

■

Remark 2.

To date, we are not yet able to strongly prove the same statement for an internal adversary. Moreover, it seems to be wrong in some cases. A known key attack by the inside adversary gives her the sums $s_2^A + \alpha_2$ and $s_1^B + \beta_3$, that together with the messages M^A and M^B , reveals the shares of the parties. So we deprecate to use the key K_{AB} directly as secret key and require to apply hash function on K_{AB} instead. In outside adversary setting, KKA reveals nothing about the parties shares.

Corollary 1 *In a public channels setting, there is no perfectly secure two- or multi-party protocol that allows the parties jointly decrease the threshold for their randomly and independently selected shares.*

PROOF

Indeed, from the Theorem 1 we know, that there is no perfectly secure key agreement protocol when the parties randomly and independently choose their secrets. Suppose, by contradiction, that the perfectly secure protocol for jointly decreasing threshold exists. Let two

parties A and B randomly and independently choose their pairs of shares (s_1^A, s_2^A) and (s_1^B, s_2^B) , respectively. With high probability, their common vector of shares $(s_1^A, s_2^A, s_1^B, s_2^B)$ corresponds to the secret sharing scheme with a threshold $t = 4$. Then they use the perfectly secure protocol for decreasing this threshold to the value $t = 3$. Finally, they executed the protocol (Table 2). We obtain a perfectly secure two party authenticated key agreement protocol, that contradicts Theorem 1. A multiparty case can be easily reduced to the two-party case. ■

We used an idea of the protocol (Table 2) in papers [10, 11] to construct MPAKE. But for general security threshold $t > 2$ we need an assistance of other parties to establish a key between any two parties A and B . So we got a large communication overhead. Therefore, we have been looking for an approach that does not have such a drawback.

Note that in all previous papers we consider only the case, when there is a global secret s that is shared to the parties with some global threshold. The first thought that came to our minds is the following. What if we can distribute the pairs of shares to the parties in such a manner, that for any two parties A and B their vector of shares $(s_1^A, s_2^A, s_1^B, s_2^B)$ corresponds to their own secret value s_{AB} with the threshold $t = 3$? It is seems to be more general and simple solution. The second idea, which came to us later, is even more interesting. Let the parties use two additively homomorphic secret sharing scheme Σ_1 and Σ_2 , and at the registration stage get their

Table 3: Two-party AKE based on two homomorphic secret sharing schemes.

1. The party A selects randomly some secret value $\alpha \in S$ and shares it with threshold $t = 2$ using the first scheme Σ_1 : $Share_1(\alpha, t, pk_1^A, pk_1^B) = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2)$. Then it sends the message $M^A = ID_A || ID_B || (s_1^A + \alpha_1) || \alpha_2$ to the party B ;
2. The party B selects randomly some secret value $\beta \in S$ and shares it with threshold $t = 2$ using the second scheme Σ_2 : $Share_2(\beta, t, pk_2^A, pk_2^B) = (\beta_1, \beta_2)$. Then it sends the message $M^B = ID_B || ID_A || \beta_1 || (s_2^B + \beta_2)$ to the party A ;
3. The party A calculates the key $K_{AB} = \alpha + Recover_2(s_2^A + \beta_1, s_2^B + \beta_2, pk_2^A, pk_2^B)$;
4. The party B calculates the key $K_{BA} = \beta + Recover_1(s_1^A + \alpha_1, s_1^B + \alpha_2, pk_1^A, pk_1^B)$.

Table 4. The example of key pre-distribution for $n = 4$.

Party	Public keys	Shares
1	$pk_1^1 = 1, pk_2^1 = 12$	$s_1^1 = 0, s_1^1 = 8$
2	$pk_1^2 = 2, pk_2^2 = 11$	$s_1^2 = 1, s_1^2 = 4$
3	$pk_1^3 = 3, pk_2^3 = 10$	$s_1^3 = 5, s_1^3 = 3$
4	$pk_1^4 = 4, pk_2^4 = 9$	$s_1^4 = 8, s_1^4 = 1$

Table 5: Results of pairwise secret recovery.

Pairs	Recovered polynomial	Secret($s = f(0)$)
{1, 2}	$f(x) = 6x^2 + 9x + 11$	11
{1, 3}	$f(x) = 9x + 4$	4
{1, 4}	$f(x) = 10x^2 + 9x + 7$	7
{2, 3}	$f(x) = 12x^2 + 9x$	0
{2, 4}	$f(x) = 11x^2 + 9x + 4$	4
{3, 4}	$f(x) = x^2 + 9x + 8$	8

shares differently: the share s_i^A corresponds to the scheme Σ_i , $i \in \{1, 2\}$. The shares of any two parties A and B are connected to each other in such a way that $Recover(s_1^A, s_1^B, pk_1^A, pk_1^B) = Recover(s_2^A, s_2^B, pk_2^A, pk_2^B)$. At the key agreement stage, any two parties execute the protocol, presented in Table 3. Similar to Theorem 2, it can be proven that this protocol is also perfectly secure for outside adversary.

It seems difficult to create a concrete protocols for each of these two approaches right away. Both requires additional research. But we show with examples that this is potentially possible.

Example 1. Consider the case $n = 4$. We

use Shamir secret sharing scheme over \mathbf{F}_{13} . Using exhaustive search, we have found many solutions that correspond to our first approach. One of them we present in Table 4. The results of pairwise secret recovery are presented in Table 5.

Example 2. Let us choose n random values r_1, r_2, \dots, r_n from $\mathcal{S} = \{0, 1\}^l$ and give the party i a share $s_1^i = r_i$. The second shares are formed in a special way: $s_2^i = s_1^i \oplus \delta$ for all i , where δ is a secret offset chosen by KDC. We see, that for any two parties $s_1^i \oplus s_1^j = s_2^i \oplus s_2^j$, and the *Recover* function is a simple XOR of shares. We can use such pre-distributed shares with a protocol (see Table 3), where both schemes Σ_1 and Σ_2 are simple $(2, 2)$ -threshold additive schemes. Of course, any legal party can find offset δ and broke the protocol, but for an outside adversary it is still impossible. In this example we are not using the parties' public keys, so this is just an illustration of the possible existence of such a protocol.

5. Conclusions

In this paper, we consider a two-party and multiparty pairwise key establishment protocols through the lens of secret sharing. Our aim is to minimize communication complexity, the memory needed for storing the secrets by the parties, and, at the same time, increase the secrecy. In previous works, perfect secrecy was achieved at the cost of a significant communication overhead. Thus we are trying to overcome this drawback.

First, we provide the basic two party key agreement protocol based on additively

Table 6: Comparison of the (MP)AKE protocols.

Property	Diffie-Hellman	Blom	Our approach				
			Table 1	From[10]	Table 2	Idea 1	Table 3
Type	2AKE	MPAKE	MPAKE	MPAKE	2AKE	MPAKE	MPAKE
Secrecy							
Outside Adv.	Comp.	Perf.	Perf.	Perf.	Perf.	Perf.	Perf.
Inside Adv.	Comp.	Perf.	Perf.	Perf.	?	?	?
MITM	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
KKA	Comp.	±	±	Perf.	Perf.	Perf.	Perf.
Freshness	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
Efficiency							
Comp. cost	$O(l^3)$	$O(tl^2)$	$O(tl^2)$	$O(tl^2)$	$O(l^2)$	$O(l^2)$	$O(l^2)$
Memory	$O(l)$	$O(tl)$	$O(tl)$	$O(tl)$	$O(4l)$	$O(4l)$	$O(4l)$
Share size	l	tl	t^2l	$2l$	$2l$	$2l$	$2l$
Communication cost							
d	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
Message size	$O(l)$	0	$O(l)$	$O(t^2l)$	$O(3l)$	$O(3l)$	$O(3l)$

homomorphic secret sharing (see Table 2) and show, that it is perfectly secure for outside adversary. Using this protocol, we obtain an interesting side result – there is no perfectly secure two- or multi-party joint threshold decreasing protocol in public channels setting. Next, we propose two new ideas for shares pre-distribution that can help us achieve our goal. In Table 6 we compare our approach with the classical Diffie-Hellman key exchange protocol and Blom key pre-distribution protocol. Here $l = \log_2(K_{AB})$, the efficiency and communication cost are evaluated per party.

We see, that if the shares pre-distribution procedures for the protocols (Tables 2–3) exist and they are resistant to the inside adversary, then these solutions will be the best one among all MPAKE. Therefore, our next goal is to find such a protocols or justify its absence. Even if one of the protocols under consideration is not resistant to the internal adversary, it can still

be used in certain situations. For instance, if the device memory is protected, the model of an outside adversary becomes relevant. Moreover, if the inside adversary can calculate the key K_{AB} using only the parties’ messages and her shares, such a protocol can be viewed as a lightweight GAKE. Indeed, in GAKE we a priori assume that all parties evaluate the common key.

Another important problem associated with low-resources devices in a dynamic ad-hoc nets is an identity management. We suppose, that a blockchain-based solution can help us to solve this problem.

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